

METACATEGORY	CATEGORY	SUBCATEGORY	LEVEL
Geographic - Demographic		<i>Geographic gaps by region (coast-interior, rural-urban, etc.)</i>	EXO
		<i>Population aging</i>	EXO
		<i>Population density - geographical dispersion</i>	EXO
		<i>Migration flows</i>	EXO
		<i>Multilingualism</i>	EXO
		<i>Multiculturalism</i>	EXO
Politic	Generic national legislation	<i>Country organization: centralized vs decentralized country</i>	EXO
		<i>Budget management and allocation to different sectors</i>	EXO
		<i>Investment in science, technology and innovation</i>	EXO
		<i>Legislative uncertainty (lack of agreement between political parties in key state matters)</i>	EXO
		<i>Accountability (project/policy success monitoring)</i>	EXO
	Educational policies	<i>Fickle' educational policies (variable depending on the ruling party)</i>	EXO
		<i>% GPD destined to education</i>	EXO
		<i>Access to non-compulsory education</i>	EXO
		<i>Policies on freedom of school choice</i>	EXO
		<i>Inclusion policies</i>	EXO
		<i>School size</i>	EXO
		<i>School autonomy</i>	EXO
		<i>Compulsory education period</i>	EXO
		<i>Centralized vs open curriculum</i>	EXO
		<i>Scholarship schemes</i>	EXO
<i>Student/teacher ratio</i>	EXO		
<i>School ranking publication</i>	EXO		

METACATEGORY	CATEGORY	SUBCATEGORY	LEVEL
		<i>Teacher promotion and transfer system</i>	EXO
		<i>Promotion of technical education</i>	EXO
		<i>Salary and job stability</i>	EXO
		<i>School ownership</i>	MICRO - SCHOOL
		<i>State/region autonomy in educational issues</i>	EXO
Socioeconomic	Country - Region	<i>GPD</i>	EXO
		<i>Underground economy</i>	EXO
		<i>Unemployment</i>	EXO
		<i>Economic crisis</i>	EXO
		<i>Cooperation between diverse economic sectors</i>	EXO
		<i>Infrastructure</i>	EXO
		<i>Margination - racism</i>	MACRO
		<i>Cultural-educational offer</i>	EXO
		<i>Armed conflict</i>	EXO
		<i>Promotion of scientific and critical thinking</i>	MACRO
		<i>Contact between different socioeconomic backgrounds</i>	EXO
		School	<i>School resources: Technology, Infrastructure, School lunches, etc.</i>
	<i>Socioeconomic distribution of students in schools: heterogeneous vs homogeneous</i>		MICRO - SCHOOL
	<i>School location</i>		MICRO - SCHOOL
	Families	<i>Family cultural and educational capital</i>	MICRO - STUDENTS
		<i>Parental jobs</i>	MICRO - STUDENTS
		<i>Work-life balance</i>	MICRO - STUDENTS
		<i>Family digital competence</i>	MICRO - STUDENTS

METACATEGORY	CATEGORY	SUBCATEGORY	LEVEL
		<i>Parental age</i>	MICRO - STUDENTS
		<i>Home resources</i>	MICRO - STUDENTS
		<i>Home infrastructures</i>	MICRO - STUDENTS
	Students	<i>Combining work and studies</i>	MICRO - STUDENTS
Educational	School	<i>School plans (coexistence, guidance, etc.)</i>	MICRO - SCHOOL
		<i>School climate</i>	MICRO - SCHOOL
		<i>Organization of school-wide activities</i>	MICRO - SCHOOL
		<i>classroom groupings based on ability</i>	MICRO - SCHOOL
		<i>Attention to diversity</i>	MICRO - SCHOOL
		<i>Leadership</i>	MICRO - SCHOOL
	Teachers	<i>Teaching methodologies</i>	MICRO - SCHOOL
		<i>Lifelong learning - pedagogic updating</i>	MICRO - SCHOOL
		<i>Teacher motivation/vocation</i>	EXO
		<i>Job overload</i>	MICRO - SCHOOL
	Families	<i>Family expectations regarding education and work</i>	MICRO - SCHOOL
		<i>Family control of student device usage</i>	MICRO - STUDENTS
	Students	<i>Student expectations regarding education and work</i>	MICRO - STUDENTS
		<i>Intrinsic/extrinsic motivation of student</i>	MICRO - STUDENTS